

Exercise 2: Reproduce experimental results from a paper "Do Channels Matter? Illuminating Interpersonal Influence on Music Recommendations"

Group 25
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1 INTRODUCTION

In this paper, reproduction of the paper "Do Channels Matter? Illuminating Interpersonal Influence on Music Recommendations" done by Hyun Jeong Kim, So Yeon Park, Minju Park and Kyogu Lee, is done. The authors investigated how the interpersonal relationships affect users' evaluation of music recommendation.

2 METHODS

The authors of the original paper used web-based survey to address the research question. Therefore, we also used web-based survey, that was conducted by our colleagues from TU Wien (Tang Fung Yee, Valentin Bauer and Josip Bobinac), that were very kind and shared collected data with us, which we are thankful for.

2.1 Survey Design

Comparing the original paper survey and survey designed by our colleagues, we have concluded that the questions are the same, however the order of the questions is not randomized as in the original paper. The survey has two sections: interpersonal and non-interpersonal, both containing the same questions. The interpersonal recommendations refer to recommendations from friends and acquaintances, while non-interpersonal recommendations refer to recommendation systems. The list of questions is given in the Table 1.

2.2 Analysis

The authors of the original paper conducted all their analysis using R. However, since common statistic analysis are done, we decided to do our analysis in Python in order to confirm that they are reproducible in another environment. The Table 2 shows summary of the survey results showing means (standard deviation) for relevance, diversity, novelty, serendipity, and convenience from a 5-point Likert scale (1 - 'strongly disagree', 5 - 'strongly agree'), and percentages for adoption rate. The coloured part of the table refers to our results and non-coloured part refers to the results from the original paper. Bold values are higher mean values between interpersonal and non-interpersonal. As it is visible, our analysis showed the same higher values as the original analysis.

3 RESULTS

The web-based survey used for our analysis was done by 54 participants, while the authors of the original paper recruited 175 participants that spoke Korean fluently. The participants of the survey that we get our data for analysis from are mostly from Europe (42 of them). Ten participants chose Asia Pacific as their geographic group and one participant selected Middle East/Africa.

3.1 Evaluation of music recommendation channels

As in the original paper, our paired t-test confirmed that participants rated relevance higher in non-interpersonal channels ($p < 0.001$), while diversity ($p < 0.001$) and serendipity ($p < 0.001$) were rated higher in interpersonal channels.

4 STATISTIC

At our project we did some additional statistics of the data set.

Measures of Correlation Between Pairs of Data

Figure 1: Measures of Correlation Between Pairs of Data

Table 1: Questions of the survey

Evaluation criteria	Relevance	Is the music recommended through the channel consistent with the context and theme of the playlist?
	Diversity	Does the music recommended through the channel diversify genre or mood of the playlist?
	Novelty	Is the music recommended through the channel new or novel?
	Serendipity	Is the music recommended through the channel unexpected but good in terms of the context of the playlist?
Usage behavior	Frequency	How often do you receive music recommendations through the channel?
	Convenience	How convenient is the process of listening to the music recommended through the channel?
	Adoption rate	What percentage of the recommended music through the channel is added to the playlist?

Table 2: Summary of survey results showing means and standard deviation for relevance, diversity, novelty, serendipity, convenience and frequency from 5-point Likert scale, as well as percentages for the adoption rate. In this table, both our, and the original research results are represented for comparison. Our results are in the highlighted part of the table. (Note: Bolded values represent higher mean values between interpersonal and non-interpersonal)

	Interpersonal	Non-interpersonal
Relevance	3.37 (0.79)	4.09 (0.78)
Diversity	3.67 (0.98)	2.93 (1.21)
Novelty	4.0 (0.78)	3.37 (1.05)
Serendipity	3.54 (0.93)	3.41 (0.9)
Convenience	3.11 (1.0)	3.82 (1.15)
Frequency	2.74 (0.96)	3.74 (0.91)
Adoption rate	37.48 (29.0)	37.98 (28.54)
	Interpersonal	Non-interpersonal
Relevance	3.47 (0.86)	4.05 (0.7)
Diversity	3.92 (0.77)	3.58 (0.90)
Novelty	4.09 (0.71)	3.94 (0.82)
Serendipity	3.65 (0.96)	3.23 (0.98)
Convenience	2.64 (0.86)	3.05 (0.83)
Frequency	2.03 (0.71)	2.65 (0.89)
Adoption rate	38.34 (22.47)	45.76 (22.51)

Visual exploration

In order to obtain more the distribution of the feature and also more proper correlation in between them, we are presenting the visual below:

Mode-Statistics

Median

Frequency

Figure 2: Frequency - Interpersonal

Figure 3: Frequency - Non-interpersonal

Convenience

